

Diamond OA Recommendations for Libraries and Research Support Institutions

This is the outcome of the *Developing a Diamond Open Access Discovery Kit* workshop held on 28th May 2025 at SURF in Utrecht. Find the slides from the workshop [here](#).

This document details **four recommendations** for libraries and research support institutions that were discussed by the participants. We aim to develop a **Tapestry** where different resources on Diamond Open Access can be shared with the community based on these recommendations.

If you have questions or comments on the workshop, please send us an email at diamondexpertisecentre@gmail.com.

1) Improve registration & reporting of Diamond OA

Target audience: Libraries and research institutions

- Improve **registration of/metadata** on Diamond OA initiatives in CRIS systems
- Improve institutional and national CRIS **reporting** on Diamond OA initiatives
- Improve faculty **registration of editorial activities** on the CRIS
- Make a **report of editorial activities** from your institution
- Add Diamond OA journals to **Journal Browser** to improve discoverability
- Find out **which Diamond OA journals are within your institution** and direct the editors to the [Diamond OA Expertise Center](#)

2) Build a business case for Diamond OA

Target audience: Decision-makers

- Map **policy bodies** and their **decisions** (e.g., mandates, incentives)
- Map **policies and policy cycles** for the different actors (e.g., open access policies and when they are set to be renewed)
- Map **other incentives** like Rewards&Recognition, Open Science, and new impact routes (e.g., social impact)
- Map the **values** of the different involved stakeholders
- Link the **benefits** of Diamond OA to the values of the different stakeholders
- Include **statistics** on Diamond Open Access outputs in the Netherlands
- Support your business case with **supplementary materials**, e.g.:
 - ◆ A memo aimed at university boards supported by Chiefs Open Science

- ◆ Short videos on values and how Diamond OA contributes to them
- ◆ Create a list with the recent bibliography on Diamond OA to inform policymakers about the latest developments in Diamond OA

3) Be active in the outreach activities of Diamond OA

Target audience: Faculties 🎓

- **Create Diamond OA Journal lists** for specific disciplines in collaboration with departments (e.g. [A Shortlist of Diamond Open Access Journals for the Faculty of Science at Utrecht University](#))
- **Disseminate Diamond OA Journal lists** via the most-used internal channels.
- Start **structured discussions in research groups** and faculty departments about Diamond OA (e.g, implement in already existing meetings of departments/courses)

Target audience: Authors 🖋️

- **Create games** on Diamond OA
 - ◆ e.g., Utrecht game (Diamond&Dinosaurs), [GHOST collective](#), [FORRT Open Research Games](#)
- **Organize presentations, workshops, and/or game sessions** on Diamond OA for research groups
- Create a **checklist/workflow** to help researchers **identify if a journal is Diamond OA**
- Promote **existing Diamond OA registries**
 - ◆ [Diamond Discovery Hub](#)
 - ◆ [DOAJ](#)

- ◆ *Journal Browser of your university*
- Create a **catalogue of Diamond OA platforms, publishers, and University Presses, divided by subject**, to help researchers find suitable publication outlets
- Create a **fact sheet on the benefits** of publishing in Diamond OA

Target audience: Editors

- Compile a **guide** on how to **set up your own Diamond OA journal** for the Dutch context
- **Promote** the [UKB Guide on How to Flip your Journal to Diamond OA](#)
- Create a **business case for editors** on Diamond OA (benefits and risks of the Diamond OA model)
- Gather and share **case studies** of best practices and **success stories**
 - ◆ [Portfolio](#) of the Diamond OA Expertise Center
- Create a **shared Diamond OA brand kit** for journals

4) Collaborate with other libraries and research institutions on Diamond OA

Target audience: Libraries and research institutions

- Improve **sharing** of cross-institutional **promotional and discovery materials** for researchers/editors
- Improve **information sharing** in case of cross-institutional **participation in Diamond OA editorial boards**.
- Create **standardized slides** to use in workshops for researchers
- Create an **overview of current projects** on Diamond OA
 - ◆ Tapestry (in progress)